

Graph of Odd Numbers of Collatz Conjecture

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Abstract

This paper studies the Collatz conjecture and introduces a specific graph structure of the odd numbers to help prove it.

1. Introduction

The Collatz conjecture, also known as the $3n+1$ conjecture, is probably the most popular unsolved problem in mathematics, because it is very easy to understand. Many of us have tried to prove it.

2. Statement of the problem

Consider the following operation on an arbitrary positive integer:

- If the number is even, divide it by two.
- If the number is odd, triple it and add one.

$$f(n) = \begin{cases} n/2 & \text{if } n \text{ is even} \\ 3n+1 & \text{if } n \text{ is odd} \end{cases}$$

Repeat the process indefinitely. The conjecture is that no matter what number you start with, you will always reach 1.

Example: the Collatz sequence for $n = 19$

$19 \rightarrow 58 \rightarrow 29 \rightarrow 88 \rightarrow 44 \rightarrow 22 \rightarrow 11 \rightarrow 34 \rightarrow 17 \rightarrow 52 \rightarrow 26 \rightarrow 13 \rightarrow 40 \rightarrow 20 \rightarrow 10 \rightarrow 5 \rightarrow 16 \rightarrow 8 \rightarrow 4 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 1$

3. Building a graph of odd numbers

Since the even numbers simply fall down to a smaller odd value, we can represent any Collatz sequence ignoring the even numbers, like this:

19 → 29 → 11 → 17 → 13 → 5 → 1

The odd number sequences like this are deterministic in one direction, but backwards it is non-deterministic, since every single element may have infinite number of parent elements. In the above example, the parent of 11 is 29, but 117 and 469 are also the direct parent of 11, because in the original Collatz sequence there is no odd number between 469 and 11. The following sequence also fits to the rules of Collatz...

469 → 11 → 17 → 13 → 5 → 1

...since if we write back the even numbers, we get back the original sequence:

469 → 1408 → 704 → 352 → 176 → 88 → 44 → 22 → 11 ...

For example the following numbers are also the parents of 11:

7, 29, 117, 469, 1877, 7509, 30037, 120149 ...

All of these numbers are such numbers which are the first even numbers before 11 in the original Collatz sequence.

It follows from the above that if P odd number is a parent of a number, the P*4+1 also a parent of it. Among the parent elements there is a smallest one, S₀. All of the possible parent element of a number can be derived from the smallest parent:

$$S_{n+1} = S_n * 4 + 1$$

Formula 1: calculating the further parent elements

Also it follows, that every odd number S_s that have 5 as remainder after division by 8, is a parent of such number, which have a smallest parent S₀, which S₀ leaves a remainder other than 5 after division by 8.

Those odd numbers that divisible by 3 have no smallest parents. These numbers can be derived only from an even number in the original Collatz sequence.

If n is an odd number and not divisible by 3, we can calculate its smallest parent¹ with this simple formula:

$$S_0(n) = \begin{cases} (n*4-1)/3 & \text{if } n \bmod 3 = 1 \\ (n*2-1)/3 & \text{if } n \bmod 3 = 2 \\ S_0(n) \text{ does not exist} & \text{if } n \bmod 3 = 0 \end{cases}$$

Formula 2: calculating the smallest parent

We can also calculate the smallest parent of a smallest parent, and we can continue this process until we arrive to a number that is divisible by 3, which have no smallest parent.

1 In this paper sometimes we refer to the smallest parent as P, especially if it is in a “smallest parent” column

The smallest parents of smallest parent of 17 are:

9
↓
7
↓
11
↓
17

Since $17 \bmod 8 \neq 5$, 17 also a smallest parent of an odd number. The next odd number of the Collatz sequence is 13, and the smallest parent of it is 17. $13 \bmod 8 = 5$, therefore it is not a smallest parent of any other number. By adding 13 to the bottom, we get a complete “smallest parent” dependency column.

9
↓
7
↓
11
↓
17
↓
13

The elements of such columns form a two-way deterministic structure, the base of them are P_b , the top element is P_t odd numbers, where $P_b \bmod 8 = 5$ and $P_t \bmod 3 = 0$

The elements of the complete columns, the smallest parents can be horizontally extended with other parents by applying the **Formula 1**, and if these parents are not divisible by 3, they can be extended also upwards with their smallest parents. For example:

Figure 1: The graph of parents

The calculation rules of rows and columns make sure that the graph is two-way deterministic in both directions. Such graphs with root elements are trees². In this tree if we apply the Collatz algorithm on any element, we always step left or down, approaching the number 1.

It follows from the above that to prove the Collatz conjecture, only the following theorems must be proved:

(Theorem 1): All of the odd numbers are placed on the tree above, so there is only one tree with one root.

(Theorem 2): There is no odd number that is placed in such a row or column which is infinite in both directions.

Since the rule system of the tree can be applied for any odd number P and these rules make sure that we can step only left (in case of $P \bmod 8 = 5$) or down ($P \bmod 8 \neq 5$), if we prove (Theorem 2), the (Theorem 1) also will be proven.

4. Proving of finiteness of the „smallest parent” dependency column

By applying the **Formula 2** repeatedly on an arbitrary odd number P_n that is not divisible by 3, after several steps we arrive to a number that is divisible by 3. During these steps the value is either increasing or decreasing. If an element, $P_n \bmod 3 = 1$, then the next element, P_{n+1} will be greater, while if $P_n \bmod 3 = 2$, then P_{n+1} will be smaller. This way, the increase-decrease direction is determined by the division-by-3-remainder of the actual element.

Since the division-by-3-remainder of the next element P_{n+1} also determines the increase direction for the subsequent element (P_{n+2}), we can conclude that the variations of $P_n \bmod 9$ determine the all possible increase/decrease variations for the next two, $P_n \bmod 27$ for the next 3 elements (3 elements have $2^2=4$ difference variations between them). By continuing this approach, it is possible to determine the increase/decrease variations for the next X steps from the 3^X remainders of the actual element, P_n .

n	P_n	Direction	$P_n \bmod 3$	3^n	$P_1 \bmod 3^n$	Available remainders for 3^{n+1}
4	135	\ominus	0	81	67	
3	203	\ominus	2	27	13	13, 40, 67
2	305	\oplus	2	9	4	4, 13, 22
1	229		1	3	1	1, 4, 7

Table 1: Example of the correlation between the remainders and the increase/decrease direction

On the example above: $P_1 \bmod 3 = 1$; if it would be 0, the column could not continue. It is 1, the next step is an increase. For an arbitrary odd number X , if $X \bmod 3 = 1$, then the possible values of $X \bmod 9$ are: 1, 4 and 7.

² The tree is acyclic, each value appears only once, no repeat. This is due to the fact that this graph is defined by a rule system that is deterministic in both directions, and have a root element.

Two of the three possible values (1 and 4) determine some (increasing or decreasing) continuation, the remaining one (7) marks the end of the column. $P_1 \bmod 9 = 4$, the column continues. If $P_1 \bmod 9$ would be 7, then the column would contain two elements, after one increasing step it would end with a number divisible by 3.

Since $P_1 \bmod 27$ is not 4 but 13, the column continues further, but since $P_1 \bmod 81 = 67$, there are no more steps.

In the table below, there is a summary about what remainder values determine which increase variations for column sizes 1-2-3-4-5. (The values in this table will be explained later on).

Mod 3	Mod 9	Mod 27	Mod 81	Mod 243
0	5 (-)	4 (+) (-)	29 (-) (+) (+)	13 (+) (-) (-) (+)
	7 (+)	8 (-) (-)	53 (-) (-) (-)	37 (+) (+) (-) (+)
		11 (-) (+)	67 (+) (-) (-)	71 (-) (-) (+) (-)
		19 (+) (+)	17 (-) (-) (+)	83 (-) (+) (+) (+)
			49 (+) (-) (+)	101 (-) (+) (-) (-)
			64 (+) (+) (-)	109 (+) (+) (+) (-)
			47 (-) (+) (-)	157 (+) (-) (+) (-)
			55 (+) (+) (+)	163 (+) (+) (+) (+)
				22 (+) (-) (+) (+)
				26 (-) (-) (-) (+)
				40 (+) (-) (-) (-)
				44 (-) (-) (+) (+)
				74 (-) (+) (-) (+)
				80 (-) (-) (-) (-)
				172 (+) (+) (-) (-)
				218 (-) (+) (+) (-)

Table 2: Some increase variations and the related remainders in modulo groups

For an arbitrary odd number we can determine the number of steps until it reaches the top of the “smallest parent” column by repeating the **Formula 2**. We only have to check the remainders of it with division by 3^n , one by one, looking for one that is existing in the table above, and the first matching gives the proper direction variation.

For example:

$$\begin{aligned}
 643 \bmod 3 &\neq 0 \\
 643 \bmod 9 &\notin \{5, 7\} \\
 643 \bmod 27 &\notin \{4, 8, 11, 19\} \\
 643 \bmod 81 &\notin \{29, 53, 67, 17, 49, 64, 47, 55\} \\
 643 \bmod 243 &= 157 \rightarrow \oplus \ominus \oplus \ominus
 \end{aligned}$$

Despite the fact that only a small fraction (2^{k-1}) of the possible remainders in the modulo groups ($\bmod 3^k$) define a specific increase variation, it is easy to see that every odd number have such.

For mod 3 there is 1, mod 9 has 2, mod 27 has 4 such defined variation, and if we continue this, the following sum gives the involved fraction of odd numbers:

$$\frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{9} + \frac{4}{27} + \dots = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{2^{k-1}}{3^k} = 1 \quad ,$$

therefore always exists an increase variation for any of the odd numbers. Since an increase variation also defines a finite number of steps, this makes sure that the top of the “smallest parent” column is in finite distance from any odd number.

The bottom of the columns, P_b are such odd numbers that for $P_b \bmod 8 = 5$. The P_b is also within finite distance from any column member, especially the top element, because of the followings:

The 1/4th of the top elements P_t are also $P_t \bmod 8 = 5$ so they themselves are bottom elements.

The 1/4th of the children of the remaining 3/4th of the top elements also bottom elements too, and the same true for the children of the rest, and so on. By this, we can sum how many top elements are paired with a bottom element:

$$\frac{1}{4} + \frac{3}{4} + \frac{9}{16} + \frac{27}{64} + \dots = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{3^k}{4^{k+1}} = 1$$

Therefore for every and each P_t element there is a P_b pair, within finite steps distance. All of the other column elements are between a P_b - P_t pair.

This means also that an infinite size “smallest parent” column does not exist.

The following table demonstrates the “meaning statistics” of the remainders in the modulo groups:

Modulo	Number of defined difference-variations	Already defined in previous modulo	Next modulo defines
3	1	0	2
9	2	3	4
27	4	15	8
81	8	57	16
243	16	195	32
729	32	633	64
2187	64	1995	128
6561	128	6177	256

For example if we analyze a number by its remainder after division by 27:

{19,4,11,8} remainders define a difference variation.

{5, 14, 23; 7,16,25 ; 0,3,6,9,12,15,18,21,24} these remainders are already specified an increase variation, since the remainders of 3 and 9 have already covered them.

{1,10, 13,22, 2,20, 17,26} these remainders take account in subsequent modulo groups, mod 81 or a higher division remainder will define its difference variation.

4.1 Defining column values from difference

The element values in the „smallest parent” columns are either monotonically increasing, decreasing or vary, from the bottom to the top, as the **Formula 2** applies.

strictly monotonically increasing					strictly monotonically decreasing				
n	P _n	Formula 2	P mod 3	P mod 8	P _n	Formula 2	P mod 3	P mod 8	
			Difference Formula				Difference Formula		
3	1281		0	1	15		0	7	
	↓ (P _{n-1} *4-1)/3		D ₃ =320 = D _{n-1} *4/3			↓ (P _{n-1} *2-1)/3		D ₃ =8 = D _{n-1} *2/3	
2	961		1	1	23		2	7	
	↓ (P _{n-1} *4-1)/3		D ₂ =240 = D _{n-1} *4/3			↓ (P _{n-1} *2-1)/3		D ₂ =12 = D _{n-1} *2/3	
1	721		1	1	35		2	3	
	↓ (P _{n-1} *4-1)/3		D ₁ =180			↓ (P _{n-1} *2-1)/3		D ₁ =18	
0	541		1	5	53		2	5	

The absolute value of the differences of the column elements (D_n) can also be calculated, which is very simple in the case of monotonically increasing or decreasing columns:

$$D_n = \left| \left(\frac{D_{n-1} * 4}{3} \right) \right| \quad \text{or} \quad D_n = \left| \left(\frac{D_{n-1} * 2}{3} \right) \right|$$

The function defined in **Formula 2**, changes only if P_n mod 3 also changes. P_n mod 3 and P_{n-1} mod 3 value can be the same if and only if their difference D_n, is divisible by 3 (D_n mod 3= 0). In monotone columns this property applies to every element except the one on the top.

Varied as ⊕, ⊕, ⊖.					Varied as ⊖, ⊖, ⊕.				
n	P _n	Formula 2	P mod 3	P mod 8	P _n	Formula 2	P mod 3	P mod 8	
			Difference Formula				Difference Formula		
3	555		0	3	201		0	1	
	↓ (P _{n-1} *2-1)/3		D ₃ =278 = (D _{n-1} +0.5)*4/3			↓ (P _{n-1} *4-1)/3		D ₃ =50 = (D _{n-1} -1)*2/3	
2	833		2	1	151		1	7	
	↓ (P _{n-1} *4-1)/3		D ₂ =208 = D _{n-1} *4/3			↓ (P _{n-1} *2-1)/3		D ₂ =76 = D _{n-1} *2/3	
1	625		1	1	227		2	3	
	↓ (P _{n-1} *4-1)/3		D ₁ =156			↓ (P _{n-1} *2-1)/3		D ₁ =114	
0	469		1	5	341		2	5	

If the decreasing changes to increasing or vice versa (so $P_n \text{ mod } 3 \neq P_{n-1} \text{ mod } 3$) then the rule for the absolute value of the differences:

increasing ⊕ → decreasing ⊖ (mod 3: 1 → 2)	Decreasing ⊖ → increasing ⊕ (mod 3: 2 → 1)
$D_n = \left \left(\frac{(D_{n-1} + 0.5) * 4}{3} \right) \right $	$D_n = \left \left(\frac{(D_{n-1} - 1) * 2}{3} \right) \right $

If the div 3 remainders of P values are changing, then the difference between them cannot be dividable by 3. Since in the columns, between every elements except the top one, the mod 3 value increasing to 2 or decreasing to 1, in these cases $D_n \bmod 3$ must be equal to 1. But in stepping to the top element, since it is divisible by 3, $D_n \bmod 3$ must be equal to 2.

4.2 Monotonically increasing or decreasing columns

In continously increasing columns with $m+1$ elements, for all of the P_n “smallest parent” values it is true, that $P_n \bmod 3 = 1$, where $n < m$. In this case the P values and the differences between them follow the rules below:

$$P_0 +D_1 P_1 +D_2 P_2 \dots +D_{m-1} P_{m-1} +D_m P_m$$

Where:

$$P_0 \bmod 3 = 1$$

$$P_n \bmod 3 = 1, 0 \leq n < m$$

$$P_m \bmod 3 = 0$$

and

$$D_k \bmod 3 = 0, 1 \leq k < m$$

$$D_m \bmod 3 = 2$$

The differences are restricted by the following rule:

$$D_1 = (P_0 - 1) / 3$$

$$D_i = \frac{D_{i-1} * 4}{3}, 1 < i \leq m$$

Since the D values are calculated from the preceding D values performing division by 3, all of them must be dividable by 3, except the last one. This is possible only if

$$D_1 = q * 3^{m-2}, \text{ where } q \bmod 3 \neq 0$$

If there are continuously decreasing elements, the rules are similar:

$$P_0 -D_1 P_1 -D_2 P_2 \dots -D_{m-1} P_{m-1} -D_m P_m$$

$$D_1 = (P_0 + 1) / 3$$

$$D_i = \frac{D_{i-1} * 2}{3}, 1 < i \leq m$$

Since such a number that have infinitely many 3s among its prime factors, does not exist, a continuously increasing or decreasing infinitely long “smallest parent” column also impossible to form.

4.3 Arbitrary varied columns

In a column which have $m+1$ elements, the difference between two P values can be negative or positive m times, 2^m difference variant is possible.

$$P_0 \pm D_1 P_1 \pm D_2 P_2 \dots \pm D_{m-1} P_{m-1} \pm D_m P_m$$

In general, if we calculate the absolute value of a difference (D_i , in the table below: y or $f(x)$) from the preceding difference (D_{i-1} , or x), then the correlations are the followings:

Table 3: The requirements of the differences for all of the possible difference variations

Difference signs			Difference mod3 change	$f(x)$, difference formula	x req $k \in \mathbb{N}$ $j \in \mathbb{N}$	y req $k \in \mathbb{N}$	k req $j \in \mathbb{N}$	Example explanation of k req
\oplus	\oplus	$\rightarrow $	$0 \rightarrow 2$	$\frac{4}{3}x$	$3k$ $9j+6$	$4k$	$3j+2$	19, +6, 25, +8, 33 $4k \bmod 3 = 2 \Leftrightarrow k \bmod 3 = 2$
\ominus	\ominus	$\rightarrow $	$0 \rightarrow 2$	$\frac{2}{3}x$	$3k$ $9j+3$	$2k$	$3j+1$	197, -66, 131, -44, 87 $2k \bmod 3 = 2 \Leftrightarrow k \bmod 3 = 1$
\ominus	\oplus	$\rightarrow $	$1 \rightarrow 2$	$\frac{2(x-1)}{3}$	$3k+1$ $9j+4$	$2k$	$3j+1$	65, -22, 43, +14, 57 $2k \bmod 3 = 2 \Leftrightarrow k \bmod 3 = 1$
\oplus	\ominus	$\rightarrow $	$1 \rightarrow 2$	$\frac{4(x+0.5)}{3}$	$3k+1$ $9j+1$	$4k+2$	$3j$	139, +46, 185, -62, 123 $(4k+2) \bmod 3 = 2 \Leftrightarrow k \bmod 3 = 0$
\oplus	\oplus	\ominus	$0 \rightarrow 1$	$\frac{4}{3}x$	$3k$ $9j+3$	$4k$	$3j+1$	307, +102, 409, +136, 545, -182... $4k \bmod 3 = 1 \Leftrightarrow k \bmod 3 = 1$
\ominus	\ominus	\ominus	$0 \rightarrow 0$	$\frac{2}{3}x$	$3k$ $9j$	$2k$	$3j$	701, -234, 467, -156, 311, -104... $4k \bmod 3 = 0 \Leftrightarrow k \bmod 3 = 0$
\ominus	\oplus	\ominus	$1 \rightarrow 1$	$\frac{2(x-1)}{3}$	$3k+1$ $9j+7$	$2k$	$3j+2$	209, -70, 139, +46, 185, -62... $2k \bmod 3 = 1 \Leftrightarrow k \bmod 3 = 2$
\oplus	\ominus	\ominus	$1 \rightarrow 0$	$\frac{4(x+0.5)}{3}$	$3k+1$ $9j+4$	$4k+2$	$3j+1$	229, +76, 305, -102, 203, -68... $(4k+2) \bmod 3 = 0 \Leftrightarrow k \bmod 3 = 1$
\oplus	\oplus	\oplus	$0 \rightarrow 0$	$\frac{4}{3}x$	$3k$ $9j$	$4k$	$3j$	217, +72, 289, +96, 385, +128... $4k \bmod 3 = 0 \Leftrightarrow k \bmod 3 = 0$
\ominus	\ominus	\oplus	$0 \rightarrow 1$	$\frac{2}{3}x$	$3k$ $9j+6$	$2k$	$3j+2$	179, -60, 119, -40, 79, +26... $2k \bmod 3 = 1 \Leftrightarrow k \bmod 3 = 2$
\ominus	\oplus	\oplus	$1 \rightarrow 0$	$\frac{2(x-1)}{3}$	$3k+1$ $9j+1$	$2k$	$3j$	1973, -658, 1315, +138, ... $2k \bmod 3 = 0 \Leftrightarrow k \bmod 3 = 0$
\oplus	\ominus	\oplus	$1 \rightarrow 1$	$\frac{4(x+0.5)}{3}$	$3k+1$ $9j+7$	$4k+2$	$3j+2$	2101, +700, 2801, -934, 1867, +... $(4k+2) \bmod 3 = 1 \Leftrightarrow k \bmod 3 = 2$

Although the formula $f(x)$ depends only on the change of the signs (in the table above: the first two “difference signs”; the “ $\rightarrow |$ ” mark means that the column have reached the top), if the third sign is also taken into consideration, then we can conclude remainder requirements for the y and x values.

For example if we want to investigate the differences between three “smallest parents”, where the last parent is a top element, then we know for sure about the y value that $y \bmod 3 = 2$. If we consider this fact and also the $f(x)$, then we can derive the required remainders for the x that is related to the given difference type.

Starting from one of the examples in the table above, from 139 to 123 there is one increasing and one decreasing step, but since $123 \bmod 3 = 0$, this is why the reminder of the preceding difference, 62, must be 2 ($62 \bmod 3 = 2$), where $y=62$. Since the first difference is positive and the next is

negative, (+46 and -62), $x \bmod 3 = 1$ ($x=46$) so $x=3k+1$. This “difference mod3 change” is marked in the table as $1 \rightarrow 2$. Since the formula is $\frac{4(x+0.5)}{3}$, $y=4k+2$. $(4k+2) \bmod 3=2$ if and only if $k \bmod 3=0$, meaning $k=3j$. From this and from $x=3k+1$ we can derive a strict rule: $x=9j+1$

Similarly, starting from 307 we have to take $\oplus \oplus \ominus$ steps, therefore after the operation $\frac{4}{3}x$, $y \bmod 3 = 1$ must be true, and necessarily $y=4k$, and $4k \bmod 3=1 \Leftrightarrow k \bmod 3=1$, meaning $k=3j+1$, so $x=9j+3$. $102 \bmod 9$ indeed equal to 3.

It is possible to create arbitrary long chains with all of the variations from the formulas and requirements above.

For example we can combine the $\oplus \ominus \ominus$ and the $\ominus \ominus \rightarrow$ | this way: since $x=9j+3$ is in the second step, and $3k+1 \rightarrow 4k+2$ is the requirement to form the y value in the first step, therefore $(2k+2) \bmod 9=3$ must be true, and these conditions are met, if $k \bmod 9 = 7$, namely $k=9j+7$. From this we form $3(9j+7)+1$, so $27j+22$ happen, therefore $x \bmod 72=22$ must be true. In the case of increasing step, the connection between the difference and the parent value is:
 $X=(P-1)/3$, $P=3X+1$ $P_0=D_1*3+1$, substituting: $3(27j+22)+1=81j+67$.

From this we can conclude that the combined $\oplus \ominus \ominus \rightarrow$ | „smallest parent” column can be formed only for those numbers which have remainder 67 after division by 81.

The element of Table 2 and its expansion to any variation can be done with the combine and chaining method explained recently, based on the requirements defined in Table 3.